

INTRA-REGIONAL MIGRATION AS A FACTOR IN THE TRANSFORMATION OF REGIONAL SOLIDARITY IN CENTRAL ASIA

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ABSTRACT

The relevance of studying intra-regional migration in the context of the formation of regional solidarity in Central Asia stems from two interrelated factors. On the one hand, since 2017 there has been a qualitative intensification of regional cooperation: regular consultative meetings of heads of state, the resolution of border disputes, and initiatives to liberalize visa regimes.

The relevance of studying intra-regional migration in the context of the formation of regional solidarity in Central Asia stems from two interrelated factors. On the one hand, since 2017 there has been a qualitative intensification of regional cooperation: regular consultative meetings of heads of state, the resolution of border disputes, and initiatives to liberalize visa regimes.¹

On the other hand, millions of residents of the region move annually between Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan, forming stable cross-border social ties that exist independently of the political will of the elites. At the same time, a gap persists in the academic literature, with migration researchers focusing primarily on economic and demographic aspects². Political scientists analyze institutional forms of cooperation, neglecting the question of how everyday migration practices transform interstate perceptions and lay the foundation for real, rather than merely declarative, solidarity.

This article aims to contribute to filling this gap. Drawing on an analysis of secondary data, materials from international organizations, and studies of migration processes in Central Asia, the author seeks to identify the mechanisms through which intra-regional migration influences the formation of regional solidarity and to determine the relationship between social (“bottom-up”) and institutional (“top-down”) factors of integration.

¹ Malysheva, D.B. “Problems of Regionalization in Post-Soviet Central Asia” // *Contours of Global Transformations: Politics, Economics, Law*. — 2020. — Vol. 13, No. 3. — P. 147.

² Mustafaev B. *Regional Identity as a Factor in the Development of Interstate Relations in Central Asia* // *Sharq Mash’ali (Eastern Torch)*. — 2021. — No. 1. — P. 148.

³In the countries of Central Asia, a stable public consensus has already formed at the intra-state level, which can be viewed as a socio-political foundation for further deepening regional integration processes.

The study concludes that intra-regional migration fosters three levels of solidarity, which collectively create a more solid foundation for regional cohesion than political declarations. The first level is infrastructural: migration flows compel states to establish mechanisms for cooperation in the border, transport, and social spheres, which objectively strengthens institutional connectivity even in the absence of formal integration agreements.

The second level is network-based: diaspora and regional communities forming in areas of attraction for migrants (primarily in the cities of Kazakhstan) create sustainable channels for cross-border communication, information exchange, and resource sharing that operate on the logic of mutual aid rather than market exchange. It is precisely these networks, as research shows, that significantly reduce the adaptation costs for new migrants and ensure the reproduction of transnational ties.⁴

The third level is cognitive: intensive interpersonal contacts transform mutual images and stereotypes, overcoming simplified notions of “neighbors” and forming a more realistic perception, which, in turn, creates a demand for predictable and friendly interstate relations.

Of fundamental importance is the fact that the region’s migratory ties have historically proved more resilient than its institutional ones. Attempts at forced integration in the 1990s and 2000s were unsuccessful precisely because they were not rooted in social reality. By contrast, the current surge in regional initiatives is taking place against the backdrop of already established migration networks and is largely driven by them.

In conclusion, we note that intra-regional migration “binds” Central Asia together more quickly and reliably, creating the social foundation upon which institutional forms of cooperation can grow. Relying on existing mechanisms of “solidarity from below” opens the prospect for a qualitatively new, organic regional community.

Bibliography:

1. Malysheva, D.B. Problems of Regionalization in Post-Soviet Central Asia // *Contours of Global Transformations: Politics, Economics, Law*. — 2020. — Vol. 13, No. 3. — Pp. 140–155.
2. Mustafaev B. Regional Identity as a Factor in the Development of Interstate Relations in Central Asia // *Sharq Mash’ali (Eastern Torch)*. — 2021. — No. 1. — Pp. 146–152.
3. Seitov A.P. Problems of Social Consolidation in Uzbekistan // *Information and Library Technologies Kutubxona.uz*. — Tashkent, 2021. — No. 2 (50). — Pp. 27–31.
- Rakhmonov A.Kh., Akramov Sh.Yu. External and Internal Factors of Migration from Central Asian Countries Abroad: A Literature Review // *Labor and Social Relations*. — 2025. — Vol. 36, No.

³ Seitov A.P. Problems of Social Consolidation in Uzbekistan // *Information and Library Technologies Kutubxona.uz*. — Tashkent, 2021. — No. 2 (50). — Pp. 27–31.

⁴ Rakhmonov A.Kh., Akramov Sh. , Yu. External and Internal Factors of Migration from Central Asian Countries Abroad: A Literature Review // *Labor and Social Relations*. — 2025. — Vol. 36, No. 2. — P. 145.